

“Anatomy, Gesture and Michelangelo’s Influence: A Red Chalk Study of a Warrior in Relation to the Albertina Drawing”

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Abstract

This study proposes a stylistic, iconographic, archival and iconological evaluation of a sanguine drawing depicting a warrior, kept in a private collection, measuring 18.67 x 9.93 cm. Through technical analyses and comparisons with Renaissance works, the drawing has been associated with a high probability with the hand of Sebastiano del Piombo, or with an artist close to him, probably inspired by a prototype attributed to Michelangelo Buonarroti preserved at the Albertina in Vienna. The investigations have revealed a controlled use of sanguine, sometimes diluted with water for shaded effects, and a graphic technique that clearly recalls Michelangelo's style, particularly in the study of the musculature and in the construction of the human body in movement. The work is distinguished by the deliberate interruption of the line before the margins, typical of the “unfinished”, and presents clear formal references to Michelangelo's anatomy, but with peculiarities attributable to the autonomous elaboration of Sebastiano del Piombo, perhaps with the support of Michelangelo himself. The comparison with works by Cesari, Procaccini, Raffaello and his students, highlights the stylistic distance of the author of the drawing in question from the Raphaellesque school. The most accredited hypothesis is that the drawing is a copy made directly from a Michelangelo original, for study purposes and not for engraving. This work fits into the context of the artistic rivalries and synergies of the early sixteenth century in Rome, offering a new contribution to the understanding of the diffusion of Michelangelo's visual language in the drawing of the time.

Introduction

The present contribution aims to analyze a sanguine drawing depicting a warrior, kept in a private collection, which presents significant affinities with the graphic production of the Michelangelo circle. The work, of notable executive quality and iconographic complexity, is part of an artistic and stylistic context deeply linked to the figurative culture of the first half of the sixteenth century, placing itself in direct dialogue with some famous drawings preserved at the Graphische Sammlung Albertina in Vienna, in particular with the work inventoried at no. 236, long attributed to Raphael, School of Michelangelo and finally to Semolei. The aim of the study is twofold: on the one hand, to provide an in-depth technical-material analysis through non-invasive diagnostic investigations, such as infrared reflectography and microscopic observation of the paper support and the medium; on the other hand, to initiate a systematic comparison of a stylistic, iconological and attributive nature with well-known works of the Renaissance tradition, with particular reference to the production of Michelangelo Buonarroti, Sebastiano del Piombo, Battista Franco, Giuseppe Cesari and Giovan Francesco Penni. During the analysis, graphic peculiarities emerged that strongly recall Michelangelo's visual language, such as the attention to the anatomical structure, the plastic tension of the limbs and the skillful use of sanguine in chiaroscuro function. The concept of "unfinished" is particularly significant, recognizable in the artist's conscious

choice to interrupt the line before the edge of the sheet, attributing to the drawing its own expressive autonomy even in the absence of formal completeness. The study avails itself of the collaboration of specialists in different fields – from art history to diagnostics, from molecular biology to the analysis of paper supports – in order to provide an integrated and multidisciplinary reading of the work, with the ultimate goal of advancing a new attribution hypothesis and placing the drawing within a more precise historical and cultural horizon.

Materials and Methods

Paper support and analysis

The drawing under study was made on artisanal paper produced with hemp, linen and cotton fibres, as revealed by the microscopic analyses conducted. The thickness of the fibres is between 10 and 20 μm , while the overall thickness of the sheet is 70 μm . The qualitative analysis also highlighted the presence of mineral additives such as calcium and talc, compatible with Renaissance papermaking practices. The paper has horizontal watermark lines spaced 2 mm apart, and vertical lines at 28 mm, characteristics that allow for typological dating. A trace of watermark is visible along the left edge, which is difficult to read due to the deterioration of the sheet. The upper and right edges show a clean cut, made with scissors, while the lower and left edges appear to have been torn manually or incised with rudimentary tools, presumably at a time after the drawing was made.

Executive technique and graphic materials

The work was executed entirely with sanguine, without the addition of graphite, ink or other pigments. In some areas, sanguine diluted with water was applied, in order to obtain nuanced effects and tonal variations. Analysis by infrared reflectography (IRR) confirmed the absence of covering materials visible in the infrared, consistent with the exclusive use of sanguine, whose hematite is transparent in this spectrum. The lines drawn present an accurate modulation of pressure and stroke, with the use of cross-hatching, depending on the volumetric and anatomical definition of the figure. The dilution of the sanguine in selected areas produced nuanced chiaroscuro effects, consistent with the plastic study of the human body in motion.

Imaging techniques and diagnostic investigations

The use of infrared reflectography has allowed the identification of secondary traces of numbers, letters and partial drawings, presumably transferred by pressure from other sheets, suggesting the hypothesis that the paper support was part of a study notebook or a scrapbook. The total transparency of the pigment confirms the absence of underdrawing (preparatory drawings), indicating a direct, instinctive but controlled execution.

Comparative analysis and stylistic comparison

An in-depth comparison was conducted with drawings attributed to Michelangelo Buonarroti, Sebastiano del Piombo, Giovan Francesco Penni, Giuseppe Cesari (Cavalier d'Arpino) and Battista Franco known as Semolei, with reference to works held at the Graphische Sammlung Albertina

in Vienna, the Casa Buonarroti in Florence, the British Museum and the Gabinetto Disegni e Stampe degli Uffizi. In particular, the drawing under study appears to be derived directly from work no. inv. 236 of the Albertina, executed in charcoal and historically attributed to Raphael, Michelangelo and finally to Semolei. The formal and morphological comparison highlighted a direct structural similarity, although with smaller dimensions and slight simplifications in the line. The research did not detect any engraving purposes in the drawing, thus excluding that it was produced for a print. The lack of systematic lines for tracing confirms that the work was probably conceived for study purposes or as an independent copy from an original, rather than as a model intended for serial reproduction.

State of conservation and restoration interventions

Technical and visual investigations have highlighted traces of restoration on the support, particularly along the edges. The adhesion of the pigment appears stable, with no signs of abrasion or overlapping. In some places, the presence of two different types of sanguine is evident, an element that could indicate a subsequent intervention, or a deliberate variation by the author, although it has not been possible to establish with certainty whether both hands belong to the same artist.

Standard Fig.
Warrior's Study
18.67cm x 9.93cm
Technique on blood paper
Private collection

According to scientific research, the support used to create this drawing is a paper created from rags, consisting of hemp fibers, linen and some cotton fibers. The thickness of these fibers varies from 10 to 20 μm . The paper contains additives such as Calcium and Talc. The thickness of the paper is 70 μm .

Fig.1

Microscopio ottico (x4)

Microscopio digitale (x230) - dettaglio dello spessore

The sheet appears trimmed with clean cuts, made with scissors on the upper and right sides. While on the left and lower sides the cut was made without scissors but probably by tearing, given the fraying, or with more rudimentary cutting tools.

Fig.2

The sheet has a laid out line. The space between the lines is 2 mm, while the space between the veins is 28 mm. A trace of watermark is identifiable on the left edge, not easy to read. This also confirms what was expressed by the technical laboratory study, regarding the fact that the sheet must have undergone a restoration intervention.

Fig.3

In some places the sanguine has been diluted with water to obtain a shaded technique. As we can see in this image with the affected points, marked with red arrows.

Fig.4

In the image on the side obtained through the infrared technique, we can see that the drawing is no longer visible, this element gives us the confirmation that the entire drawing was made with the sanguine technique without the use of other materials for the line. In fact, the hematite that constitutes the sanguine appears to be transparent to infrared vision.

Thanks to the reflectography that was performed on the work, it was also possible to highlight the presence of traces of numbers, writings and drawings that remained impressed on the paper, probably because this sheet was part of a notebook or other in which notes were taken or elements were noted, in this way it is possible to explain the transfer of these by pressure.

Fig.5

What immediately appears when looking at this drawing is that we find a controlled use of lines, with meticulous creation of crossed signs in some overlapping and thickened points necessary to describe the musculature, creating a sure manipulation that infuses a classical quality to the work. We find elements of strong appeal, specifically with the classical style of Michelangelo.

Fig.6

In the images above, we can observe how in this drawing, and specifically in the outer edges, close to the edge of the sheet, the line stops well before the edge. This aspect is very interesting, especially linked to a sign language that we could define as "unfinished". The interruption of the

line before the edge of the sheet, shows the author's desire to ensure that the drawing, even if as a sketch, can have its own centrality. Furthermore, the interruption of the line, makes us assume that it is a drawing made as a sketch, otherwise the artist would have used a larger sheet, or would have reduced the size of the work, given that the drawing is partly missing not because of a removal of the outer part, but because of an interruption of the graphic line, as can be clearly seen in the images above. On the lower edge, the drawing of the foot therefore ends before the edge, this makes us understand that the work was finished at that point and not that there was a continuation of the drawing on the other side of the sheet. We can also assume that the left and lower cut, made in tearing, was carried out in succession to the creation of the drawing.

Fig.7

This aspect of the unfinished can be found in several artists, one of the most famous who brought this concept outside of drawing was

Michelangelo Buonarroti who impressed this characteristic also in his sculptural work as well as in frescoes and drawings. Behind this idea of the “unfinished” we often find a reflection on the tension between creative potential and the impossibility of fully realizing the work. Furthermore, in the case of Michelangelo, he often worked under pressure, with strict deadlines that could influence his ability to complete all his works with the perfection he imagined. Therefore, this leaving unfinished can be seen as a way to represent the incompleteness of the human condition and as a sort of challenge to absolute perfection.

The drawing of the analyzed work presents the subject of a warrior with specific anatomical elements and studies of the muscular structure and physicality. The drawn muscles have intricate shading to reflect depth and dimension, indicating the dynamic form as a characteristic element found in Michelangelo's works. This study represents a great example of how to capture the realism and vitality of the human body, acting as preparatory work as for the most renowned masterpieces of Buonarroti.

Fig.8

Michelangelo's works and style

This drawing of a male nude with his back arched like a bow is based on both classical and living models.

Fig.9

Study for the Last Judgement Pietà
Buonarroti House - Florence
39.8cm x 28.2cm - Ink

In this image we can see how not a single sanguine is actually used but the presence of two different types of sanguine. It is not possible based on the analyses conducted to understand whether these two sanguine were used by the same artist, or at two different times, perhaps during a restoration. The two arrows that we find above indicate the two types of sanguine used. In some places this sanguine has been passed with water providing a shaded effect.

Fig.10
Study of a Male Nude 1503-1504

Pen and ink - 16" x 11" -Buonarroti House - Florence

It presents a connection with the compositional study of the Battle of Cascina. Michelangelo kept this drawing in his workshop and reused it about 25 years later.

Fig.11
Study for the Last Judgement Pietà
Casa Buonarroti – Florence -39.8 cm x 28.2 cm - Ink

This drawing was created by Michelangelo in Rome. Made with ink on paper, this piece belongs to the late Renaissance art movement and serves as a sketch and study. The subject is part of the series of drawings for the frescoes of the Sistine Chapel currently housed at Casa Buonarroti in Florence. The subject that we find in this work in the studio, obviously is a warrior who is fighting. If we think of combat scenes, among the most emblematic images, Michelangelo comes to mind, and among the works he created with the presence of battles, the Battle of Cascina immediately comes to mind.

Fig 12 Michelangelo

Composition Study for the Battle of Cascina
1504-1505 - Florence
Pen and Silver Tip on Paper
23.5cm x 35.6cm.

Uffizi Gallery (Cabinet of Drawings and Prints)
In this complete sketch by Michelangelo, you can see some variations compared to the prints. For example, in the right portion, some figures are added to those seen in the prints.

In 1503-1504 Pier Soderini commissioned Michelangelo and Leonardo to paint two cycles of frescoes, one depicting the Battle of Cascina and the other the Battle of Anghiari, commissioned for the Salone dei Cinquecento in Palazzo Vecchio in Florence. Unfortunately, the commission was not completed by Michelangelo because the following year he was called to Rome (1505) by Pope Julius II to create his own funerary monument to be placed in the new Basilica of St. Peter. Michelangelo studied the human body in all its positions and all its possibilities of expression. In the Battle of Cascina, Michelangelo did not want to represent a study of landscape, or atmosphere, or light effects, but he wanted to convey the sense of space with the bodies, their movement and their interaction. Very interesting in the drawing under study is the study of the twisting movement of the torso, head and shoulders. The main purpose of this drawing, therefore, remains the study of the musculature and the shadow effects created by the torsion of the torso.

Fig.13

Michelangelo
Study for the Battle of Cascina
Oxford Ashmolean Museum
Pen and brown ink
17.8cm x 25cm

Fig.14

Michelangelo
Figure study for the Battle of Cascina
Paris – Louvre
Metal tip and ink
34cm x 18cm

Fig.15

Michelangelo
Sheet with other studies and study of the movement of
bodies in space. Oxford Ashmolean Museum
Red pencil - 24.5 cm x 33.5 cm

When we talk about the Battle of Cascina we must consider the voice of the artists of the time, and their thoughts about this work. Benvenuto Cellini wrote about the cartoons of both Michelangelo and Leonardo da Vinci, calling them the School of the World. The Battle of Cascina was described by Cellini in the following way:

“this cartoon was the first beautiful work of Michelangelo, who showed his marvelous virtues, and he made it in competition with another one made by Leonardo da Vinci, which was to serve for the Council Chamber of the Palazzo della Signoria”.

Michelangelo on his preparatory works regarding the Battle of Cascina, reports in the scene, a quantity of soldiers who because of the summer heat, had undressed and stripped to cool off in the Arno river and the representations, make us relive those frenetic moments of the alarm of the attack. These naked infantrymen in beautiful gestures, had never been seen in antiquity and not even in the modern era by any artist. The style of the works of the two cartoons compared were studied by the greatest of the time.

Fig.16
 Mark Anthony Raimondi
 From Michelangelo's Cartoon for the Battle of Cascina
 - Uffizi Gallery - Florence

A feeling of admiration towards such works, we also find it in Raphael of Urbino who in 1506 visited Florence, who, in his cartoons, was able to assimilate from both masters, elements without losing anything of his own grace. Indeed, the trip to Florence, was for him very prolific and constructive. The knowledge relating to the cartoon of the Battle of Cascina, comes to us indirectly through the work of the artists who copied the elements and the engravings that were created over time. The prints of Michelangelo's work do not evoke the battle, but the sudden appeal to the camp while bathing in the Arno; it was an excellent choice by Michelangelo, who in this way managed to represent the heroic beauty of the nude in movement. Observing the drawing in the studio it can be said that it is not a translation drawing for future engraving, but perhaps to make a copy from an original. This element excludes the purpose of the drawing studied to be used for printing and engraving purposes. We can

therefore exclude that the artist who created this drawing is an engraver, since otherwise he would have had to maintain an adherence to the intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics of the original work, maintaining a personal style and with distinctive characters, which we do not have in this drawing. The drawing must therefore be a translation from an original. From the first glance, this work can be identified as not subject to being defined as a print that imitates a drawing, since printing requires a complex engraving technique perfected over time, therefore there were artists who specialized precisely in this technique, one for all in the case of Raphael, was Marcantonio Raimondi.

Fig.17
 Anthony Venetian
 From Michelangelo's cartoon for the Battle of Cascina
 Uffizi Gallery

Fig.18
Louis Schiavonetti
From Michelangelo's cartoon for the Battle of Cascina
Uffizi Gallery
In this print by Schiavonetti the entire group of warriors is represented preparing to run towards battle.

Rodolfo del Ghirlandaio, son of his master Domenico, from whom Michelangelo probably copied elements. The Battle of Cascina was born from the episode of the "bathers" that is narrated in the chronicle of Filippo Villani, where the day before the Battle, due to excessive heat, most of the Florentine soldiers who were camped in Cascina, had disarmed. But on that occasion, faced with imminent danger, Michelangelo exploited this situation as an unparalleled pretext for representing naked bodies in movement.

In reality, the Battle of Cascina took place over two days, but in his depiction, Michelangelo combines the two into one dramatic event.

Fig.18
Bastiano da Sangallo's copy of Michelangelo's "Battle of Cascina" - 1542
78.7cm – 12.9cm
Ear of Leicester Collection
Holkham Hall

Among Michelangelo's early drawings we find his reproductions of the characters from Masaccio's "Tribute" in the Brancacci Chapel at the Carmine, and of Giotto's stories of St. John the Evangelist in the Peruzzi Chapel in Santa Croce, Florence. In Buonarroti's early pen studies, we can see a graphic technique for rendering chiaroscuro effects and volumetric emphasis, using dense cross-hatching with short lines, very similar to those of some sketches by his contemporary

Fig.19
Michelangelo, Figure Study for the Battle of Cascina
Vienna – Graphische Sammlung Albertina

Fig.20

Michelangelo
Figure study for the Battle of Cascina
London – British Museum

The subject represented in the drawing in the studio cannot be associated with a character from the Battle of Cascina, for various reasons. The Battle of Cascina took place on 28 July 1362 between the forces of Florence and those of Pisa, two of the main powers of the 14th century. At the time, Florence was commanded by Galeotto Malatesta, while Pisa was commanded by Giovanni d'Acuto. The battle was won by Florence, which managed to repel the Pisan attack near Cascina near Pisa. The clothes worn by the fighters in this battle were typical of late medieval fashion. In the battle of Cascina drawn by Michelangelo, however, the soldiers were shown in the act of undressing to bathe, so in the preparatory drawings we find all the subjects naked or semi-naked, highlighting the anatomy more than the equipment, but it was a symbolic choice not realistic from a military point of view. In addition to the fact that the soldiers were

naked, we have as other negative elements to this hypothesis, the type of clothing worn by the warrior under study, clothing that seems to recall the Roman era.

Fig.21
The Conversion of Saul (or Saint Paul), detail, is a fresco (625x661 cm) by Michelangelo Buonarroti, datable to 1542 - 1545 and located in the Pauline Chapel in the Vatican.

In this fresco we find how the soldier wears the same elements of the kilt that we find in the work under study, with the only difference that in the drawing we have a bare chest. This fresco brings us further confirmation regarding the identity of the warrior who, most likely, can be associated with a Roman warrior rather than a Florentine soldier. In the drawing under study, it is not possible to identify the warrior's weapon because it was probably unsheathed positioned in the right hand which unfortunately is not visible in the drawing. The shield that we find in the drawing seems to resemble a shield used by the Romans in the 4th century called clipeus, an oval shield of the auxiliary troops. The shields were made of wood, covered with painted leather with the edges tied with rawhide.

Fig.22

Naked Man Standing Backwards
Around 1503
Michelangelo Buonarroti
Pen and brown ink over traces of a preparatory
drawing in black chalk
38.7cm x 19.5cm

Students and copyists of Michelangelo's style and works

Michelangelo, one of the greatest artists of the Italian Renaissance, had no “copyists” in the modern sense of the term.

However, many of his drawings and works have been copied or reproduced by other artists for various purposes, such as studies for the transmission of ideas and diffusion of his style.

Some of his students and followers have strongly imitated and copied him in their major works. Among them we can include the following names:

- Giorgio Vasari, who deeply admired Michelangelo, describing him in his writings as a central figure in the artistic panorama of his time.
- Daniele da Volterra, often considered one of Michelangelo's main students, was significantly influenced by the master and took many of his stylistic elements which he brought back into his works.
- Marcello Venusti, another pupil of Michelangelo who copied the master's works.
- Sebastiano del Piombo was not technically a pupil of Michelangelo but their relationship was very close and rich in artistic and intellectual collaborations with a relationship between master and disciple.

Furthermore, there were many artists working in Rome and other Italian cities in the post-Renaissance period who were influenced by Michelangelo.

Michelangelo, precisely because of his genius, always refused to take any artist to put him in his workshop as a spectator and observer, which is why today we do not have a real group of his disciples who have continued his art, as instead happened with Raphael.

This information comes to us from the words of a historian, Paolo Giovio, who highlighted how substantial the difference was between Michelangelo's work and that of other artists who worked within well-organized workshops.

Similar works by Raphael

Fig.23
Nude Study - Raffaello Sanzio
Corsini Fund – First half of the 16th century.
26.2cm x 20.3cm

An important collection of drawings by Raphael comes from the collection of the Albertina museum in Vienna. It must be said, however, that of the 144 works present that were initially associated with the artist, after careful examination over time it has been highlighted that only a few of these can be ascribed to the hand of the artist from Urbino. The Albertina collection preserves one of the most important collections of Italian Renaissance drawings, including numerous studies by Raphael and Michelangelo. Over the centuries, many artists have copied and reinterpreted these works, contributing to the diffusion and understanding of the Renaissance visual language.

These works were inherited from the first collections, that of Crozat, Mariette, Giuliano da Parma and the Prince of Ligne. Raphael immediately attracted forgers and it seems that even Andrea del Sarto made copies, as the Carracci did to earn money.

For Raphael, drawing was above all an indispensable tool in the creative and productive process. It is in fact through a methodical and symmetrical punctual elaboration that he carried forward in the drawings, with effective solutions, which took shape in the final phase in the panels, frescoes and tapestries.

His drawings can range from the first sketch to the actual cartoon, that is, to the final project that will then be realized on the same scale in another technique, up to barely sketched sketches. Let us remember that isolating Raphael's autograph sign within the drawings is not easy nor always possible. Behind Raphael's drawings there were many names that ranged in time, who took care of them and valorized the work and their custody. Among these names we could mention people from different historical periods, such as Timoteo Viti, who over time recognized their great value and who used them as models. Timoteo Viti was a fellow countryman of Raphael and occasionally collaborated with him. We also find the artist Peter Lely, a famous English artist of the 17th century, and Sir Thomas Lawrence, the fashionable portraitist of the early 19th century. We therefore have different places and circumstances, where each of them collected Raphael's drawings and then made them flow into many important collections. If we take Raphael's London collections as an example, we can observe how many of these drawings derived from the collection of Timoteo Viti, and that they always remained within his family and arrived in England in 1823 when the art dealer Samuel Woodburn secured the collection in Pesaro from the last heirs.

Works and Style of Giuseppe Cesari (Cavalier d'Arpino)

Below are some examples to use as a comparison with the studio drawing, as the work had previously been attributed to this artist.

The artistic career of Cavalier d'Arpino, we can say that it begins with his entry into Rome in the workshop of Circignani. His initial role was that of a boy, at that time he was employed at the loggias on the third floor of the Vatican Palace.

His artistic technique and work became highly appreciated in Rome and the figures he created show a strong formal academicism and overall lack monumentality.

Fig. 24
These two images refer to the work of Sketch of Male Nude - 26 cm x 14.2 cm
Charcoal Technique
Cabinet of Drawings and Prints of the National Collection

Under Clement VIII Aldobrandini the Caesar, became the most important official painter in Rome especially by commissions and large decorative enterprises. In these drawings we witness a charcoal technique regarding quick sketches, these quick sketches do not allow for an optimal comparison.

Fig.25
Joseph Caesar
Detail Adam and Eve Expulsion from Paradise
1602-1603, 17.3 cm X 12.8 cm Kunsthaus Zurich

Fig.26
Comparison of the studio work and the Expulsion of Adam and Eve by Giuseppe Cesari.

The drawing compared turns out to be a careful drawing with more details than a sketch, and we can therefore better understand some specific drawing techniques. In both works we find the trimming in some points of the edges, this gives a greater shadow effect and a streamlining of the lines. We find in both works an interesting shading of the musculature, particularly careful and areas instead those in shadow, which have a heavier stroke. The touch appears light with an increase in the irregularities in the lines and an increase in the sinuosity regarding the parts of the flutters that are moved by the wind. In both works we find a clear stroke regarding the contour lines, accurate and precise. But there remains the evident difference in the hand that creates the two drawings: we are in fact clearly faced with two very distinct artists in terms of style and method of realization.

Fig.27: *Giuseppe Cesari the Cavalier of Arpino*
Moses with the Tablets of the Law
1580 - Kunstpalast Dusseldorf
21 cm x 15.3 cm - Black and sanguine stone - France – Lille

Fig.28
Comparison between the Combat of the Horatii and Curiatii by Giuseppe Cesari and the studio drawing.

Fig.30
Drawing by Giuseppe Cesari, the Cavalier d'Arpino
Male nude seen from behind
Private collection

Fig. 29
Giuseppe Cesari the Cavalier of Arpino
Battle of the Horatii and Curiatii
1612-1613
Capitoline Museum of Rome

This comparison does not serve to describe that this is a preparatory drawing for this work, but it serves to highlight the similarities of the subjects represented, helping to outline the type of warrior drawn. From the arrows we find the kilt with double ornaments, the band passing over the chest, the plume above the helmet and the band on the arm of the garment. The drawings of Giuseppe Cesari of his late age appear to be characterized by an economy and a certain geometricization of the shapes and volumes. From the style, it is therefore evident that this is a Roman warrior and that the style of realization is different.

Fig.31
On the left the drawing in the studio, on the right the drawing of Cavalier D'Arpino.

In the image above, we compare the work in the studio with a drawing by Cesari. As you can clearly see, the stroke, the shading, the lines, the contours and the execution method are totally different. Furthermore, and a fundamental detail, is the warrior's skirt, a key point in the drawing on the right, which can be associated with the executive details of the Cavalier d'Arpino. It is therefore assumed that Casari saw the drawing in the studio and was inspired by the style of the drawing in the studio. A very different graphic ductus.

Fig.32
Giuseppe Cesari the Cavalier of Arpino
Study of Arm and Foot
Stadel Museum

Cavalier d'Arpino was one of the liveliest and most prolific draftsmen of his time, and during his career of over sixty years, the painter devoted himself without interruption to the practice and teaching of drawing. Giuseppe Cesari often used to hatch the background. However, in his studio drawings we do not find this peculiarity. Giuseppe Cesari's drawings often feature the use of two different colored Graphic Mediums, for example black pencil and sanguine. The use of black pencil is not only a coloristic choice, but also proves to be an indispensable technical trick to camouflage the tracing line. For example, when the texture was thick, this served to hide the trace of the red tracing. In the studio work, the presence of two mediums is not found.

Fig.33
Giuseppe Cesari the Cavalier d'Arpino
Hercules and Antaeus Red pencil and black pencil.

40.2cm x 25.6cm
The work was formerly attributed to Daniele da Volterra, the drawing is one of the preparatory studies for one of the

lunettes of the Orsini lodges. The sheet was copied by Cesari in two different versions, one of which is preserved in the Cabinet des Dessins of the Louvre Museum.

Fig.34
Roman knight in armor with drawn sword charging
Red chalk, brown paper
44.7cm x 35.3cm
Albertina – Vienna (Origin from Albert of Saxony Giuseppe Cesari the Cavalier of Arpino)

Fig.35
Ercole Procaccini – The Elder (1520-1595)
Conversion of St. Paul
Oil painting on canvas
Altarpiece
Basilica of St. James the Greater (Bologna)

Another artist who deserves a comparison with the studio drawing style, Ercole Procaccini the Elder. The Altarpiece in the photo above, was created by Procaccini following a Tibaldesque compositional layout (from **Pellegrino Pellegrini** , called Tibaldi (Puria, 1527 – Milan, 1596), was an Italian architect and painter) and in memory of the Roman culture of the mid-century. Ercole Procaccini the Elder, was born in Bologna and then moved to Milan where he worked for most of his career. His style appears to be late Renaissance with Mannerist influences, characterized by compositional elegance and delicate colors.

The Procaccini family was one of the most important artistic dynasties of northern Italy between the 16th and 17th centuries.

In Procaccini's works, one can find influences attributable to Michelangelo and, to a lesser extent, to Sebastiano del Piombo. Ercole is often compared to Michelangelo for the sculptural rendering of the bodies and the use of color; this stylistic affinity suggests a profound knowledge of Michelangelo's works by Procaccini.

Fig.36: Comparison between the work in the study on the right and the work by Ercole Procaccini on the left
 We must consider that the Procaccini family, who moved from Bologna to Milan in 1585, was a protagonist of the artistic renewal in Lombardy during the Borromean era. Their workshop was therefore a center of artistic production and diffusion, where the influences of the great Renaissance masters were studied and reinterpreted. Therefore, Procaccini could also have seen the drawing in the studio.

There have been many artists, who over time have been inspired by these drawings by copying them or making changes to them. Below are some examples of this.

Fig.37
Male Nude Study - Lelio Bears (1508-1511)
Cabinet of Drawings of the Corsini Collection
The subject taken from a drawing by Raphael.

Lelio Orsi, was a very famous Italian designer, educated between Mantua and Emilia, and his graphic and pictorial style strongly takes on elements of Giulio Romano, Correggio and Parmigianino. Between 1545 and 1546 Lelio made a trip to Rome where he had the opportunity to study the works of Michelangelo, being particularly impressed by the Cappella Paolina of the Vatican Palaces. Another artist who created works inspired by Raphael and Michelangelo was Alberti Cherubino.

Fig.38 Male figure with a soldier's headdress - Alberti Cherubino - Location: Alberti Family
Work copied from a work by Raphael - Sanguinary
Technique - 36.2 cm x 25.6 cm

Alberti Cherubino born in Sansepolcro from which his nickname Borghegiano, son of art studied in Rome with Cornelius Cort and Agostino Carracci. Over the years he made drawings and engravings inspired by works by Raphael, Michelangelo, Polidoro da Caravaggio, Andrea del Sarto and Rosso Fiorentino. Over time he also became prince of the Accademia di San Luca.

Fig.39
Studies of Male Busts - Alberti Cherubino
Cabinet of Drawings and Prints, Alberti Family.
Derivation from Michelangelo -1591 BC
28.2cm x 42cm
Brown ink pen, sanguine, pencil
Presence of a watermark with an anchor inscribed in a circle surmounted by a star.

Fig.40
Alberti John
The Twilight of the Medici Chapel
Derivation from Michelangelo Buonarroti
20cm x 28.6cm
Black and blood pencil
Giovanni Alberti worked in Sansepolcro and Mantua

Fig.40
Leg Study
Alberti Cherub
Original Author Michelangelo Buonarroti
43.8cm x 28.8cm
Black pencil
Presence of lily watermark

Fig.41
Study of a nude male figure seen from behind
Alexander Laurels
Paper and black pencil
The sheet is attributed to Allori by two ancient inscriptions

Fig.42
Girolamo Romani called the Romanino
Paper and pencil
32.4 cm x 22 cm - National Gallery of Puglia
The sheet bears an ancient attribution to Michelangelo
Buonarroti
Note how the derivation from Michelangelo's drawings
is absolutely present, but the artist's style is very
different from the Tuscan artist.

Fig.43
Daniele from Volterra (Daniele Ricciarelli)
14cm x 21.2cm
Red Chalk
 Daniele da Volterra (Il Braghettone) is best remembered for his association with Michelangelo's late works. Initially a pupil of Sodoma and Baldassarre Peruzzi, he later became an apprentice to Perin del Vaga. Michelangelo provided him with sketches on which Daniele based some of his paintings.

Daniele da Volterra is famous for having covered the genitals of the Last Judgement fresco with clothes and fig leaves in 1565, just one year after Michelangelo's death. Thanks to his censorship, the frescoes were not completely removed, as was initially planned, and could be preserved until today. These sketches for technique appear to be very calibrated, not directly associable to the Michelangelo style except in the subject.

Fig.44
Detail of the engraving by Marcantonio Raimondi on
the original work by Raphael

A subject that presents some characteristics similar to the work in the study although in a different position, comes from copies and engravings made on a work by Raffaello Sanzio. The work in question is the Massacre of the Innocents. The Massacre of the Innocents is a burin print by the engraver Marcantonio Raimondi, invented by Raffaello, which has come down to us in several copies and states.

Raphael's drawing of the Massacre of the Innocents is a preparatory work for a painting depicting a tragic scene from the Gospel, which immortalizes the moment when, on the orders of King Herod, all the male children of Bethlehem under the age of two were to be killed in an attempt to eliminate the newborn Jesus.

Raphael made a preparatory drawing later used by his followers for a large altar. In the drawing,

Raphael places Herod at the center of the scene surrounded by soldiers carrying out the atrocious massacre.

The composition is particularly complex, with moving figures that convey drama and suffering. The youthful drawing highlights Raphael's precocious talent and his innovative approach to representing movement and emotion.

The soldier unsheathing his sword presents a very important torsion study that can be compared to the drawing under study. Therefore, the hypothesis that in the beginning preparatory sketches were made with a similar situation but with different attributes such as clothing, headgear and variations should not be eliminated.

Fig.46

*Male Nude from Behind - Girolamo Romanino
21cm x 12.9cm - Red Chalk
Albertina Museum*

Fig.45

*Warrior striding
Anonymous
Albertina – Vienna*

In this drawing we find, from the point of view of the subject's clothing and settings, large similar elements, but we do not find a similarity in the graphic ductus.

Fig.47

*Baccio Bandinelli - Two Standing Male Nudes
42.2 cm x 27.9 cm - ink, pen*

Fig.48
 Augustine Venetian
 a model by Raffaello Sanzio
 1515-1530 - Copper plate engraving
 15.4cm x 10.4cm

In this slab we find the presence of a probably Roman warrior.

Fig.50
 Beautiful
 Andrea Meldolla called Schiavone
 22.4cm x 11.7cm
 Etching

In this work we find interesting elements very similar to the work in the studio, especially in the flourishes that surround the figure.

Fig. 49
 Augustine Venetian
 Copy from Marcantonio Raimondi
 1515-1530
 Copper engraving
 25.2cm x 18.2cm
 Albertina Museum

Fig.51
 Andrea Schiavone - The Rape of Helen - 1547

Andrea Meldolla, known as Schiavone, was an Italian painter and engraver active in Venice and was considered one of the protagonists of Venetian Mannerism.

Fig.52
*Battle of Shield and Lance - Giovanni Jacopo Caraglio
 - Inspired by Raffaello Sanzio*

Caraglio was a great Italian engraver, goldsmith and medalist, active in Verona, Rome and also in Poland. He was important for his ability to translate into prints the drawings of masters such as Raphael, Rosso Fiorentino, Parmigianino and Titian.

This highly dynamic work, preserved at the Art Institute of Chicago, depicts a violent clash between soldiers armed with lances, swords and shields, both on horseback and on foot. The engraving of this work by Caraglio is inspired by the frescoes in the room of Constantine in the Vatican, executed from a design by Raphael by his collaborators, in particular Giulio Romano. The subject takes up a detail of the Battle of the Milvian Bridge, a fundamental historical event for the Christianization of the Roman Empire.

Through his mastery Caraglio managed to infuse great movement and strong tension to the scene, he contributed greatly to the spread of the Mannerist style in Europe; also influencing the French school of Fontainebleau, despite never having worked directly in France. The subject represented in this work is not the work of Caraglio but he is responsible for the translation into printed form through engraving, it is probably a copy from a model by Raphael now lost, but his invention has come down to us thanks to the burin of Jacopo Caraglio who created it between 1525 and 1527. It could therefore represent a subject for the idea for a detail of the composition of the Battle of Ponte Milvio, however discarded, the anomaly is that the drawing does not present the dictates of Raphael but of another school inspired by

Michelangelo. In this battle, Emperor Constantine crushed the usurper Maxentius with his troops in 313 AD. In the cabinet of prints and drawings of the Uffizi there is a drawing with the same subject that bears an ancient but not possible attribution to Perin del Vaga, all this to lead towards an original work by Raphael. The role of prints and engravings has been fundamental for the transmission, knowledge and reconstruction of the work of many Renaissance masters, in particular Raphael Sanzio, whose production has been partly lost or remained unfinished. Many of Raphael's works have been destroyed over time, especially frescoes and preparatory cartoons including many drawings. Engravings and prints allow us to only partially reconstruct these lost compositions, also because the engravers had to translate the work in their own way by making changes.

Fig.53
*Vision of the Cross
 Hall of Constantine – Vatican-Fresco
 Performed by Raphael's students (Giulio Romano,
 Giovanni Francesco Penni, Raffaellino del Colle)*

The Hall of Constantine, present in the Raphael Rooms in the Vatican, was decorated by him and his students, who after his death used the master's cartoons to complete the decorations and completed the work in 1524. The commission was entrusted to Raphael by Leo X in 1517, as was remembered by both Vasari and Giovan Francesco Penni. However, in the last years of his life, Raphael very often entrusted the task to his students. The design of the decorative complex is attributed to Raphael, but the entire draft is probably, even the composition of the scene on the wall, the responsibility of the students. In 1524, at the time of Clement VII, the decoration must have already been completed, when Giulio Romano left for Mantua. The Hall of Constantine

is dedicated to the victory of Christianity over paganism and the affirmation of the primacy of the Roman church, with clear references to the delicate contemporary situation. Vasari attributed the vision of the cross to Giulio Romano, a position later taken up by all subsequent critics with interventions perhaps by Raffaellino del Colle.

Fig.54
Constantine defeats the tyrant Maxentius with angels carrying swords

Julius Bonasone
1544
37.3cm x 44.5cm
Metropolitan Museum
Engraving

The work above is an engraving by Giulio Bonasone, partly inspired by Marcantonio Raimondi and the Roman sarcophagus (now kept at Villa Medici in Rome) which was one of Raphael's main sources of inspiration for the project. Bonasone shows much less interest in sculptural forms. His more lyrical version of the subject is composed of soft, modeled figures with more fluid motifs. Giulio Bonasone was active mainly in Bologna in the 16th century and was one of the most important engravers of Italian Mannerism.

In the scene of the clash between Constantine and Maxentius at the Milvian Bridge, a battle scene is portrayed with soldiers armed with shields and lances, with running horses, in a very dynamic composition, typical of the Mannerist style.

As previously mentioned, the initial compositional nature is almost certainly inspired by lost

cartoons and projects for the Battle of Ponte Milvio. Unfortunately, today we only have indirect evidence from Raphael's students and engravers of the time, with differences in style. Therefore, whoever made the drawing must have seen these initial subjects, but they were reinterpreted by another school. Although he received the commission to make the projects for the "Hall of Constantine", Raphael died before completing them. The scenes in the room were executed by his school, in particular by Giulio Romano, one of his best students. Giuseppe Bonasone, for the creation of these engravings, could have drawn inspiration from preparatory cartoons, sketches and compositions known in Raphael's workshop. Between these settings that we find in these engravings and the studio drawing, we have many analogies and points in common, even if it is not possible to trace the warrior with certainty of compatibility and his style is much more Michelangelo-like. This lack of a higher comparison match comes from the fact that what we know today in prints is the result of copies and re-interpretations carried out on works in turn copied by students starting from Raphael's originals; some elements of contact with this design are always missing, which instead we find in Michelangelo's technique.

Fig.55 : *Fragment of the preparatory cartoon by Giulio Romano relating to the Hall of Constantine*

Therefore, it is highly plausible that the warrior we see in the studio drawing is a subject of the initial prototypes for the Hall of Constantine, but not made by Raphael. The influence of the artist from Urbino on the graphic arts of the time is also evident in the compositions, in the drama of the posture and in the classical heroism that shines through in these scenes.

Fig.56: *Cartoon by Giovan Francesco Penni – Louvre Hall of Constantine*

When we think about the work of the Battle of Ponte Milvio, we must always keep in mind that the work was commissioned to Raphael by the Pope. In that period, Raphael very often entrusted his collaborators with the task of working for him, both at the level of preparatory cartoons and at the operational level in fresco.

So we cannot know exactly how much of Raphael there is in that work. It seems highly probable that Raphael made some initial sketches and the draft of the organization of the subjects to then be taken up and re-proposed by Giulio Romano and Penni.

Today we know nothing about these initial sketches by Raphael, so it remains an open and debated theory. His two main collaborators were Giulio Romano and Giovan Francesco Penni who collaborated directly, also inheriting Raphael's unfinished works.

Giovan Francesco Penni, known as the Factor, entered Raphael's workshop at a very young age and his artistic personality has proved elusive, but it is known that he preferred drawing to painting and in fact he produced many finished drawings. After the end of his partnership with Giulio Romano in 1524, Penni was clearly incapable of pursuing an independent career.

He later followed Giulio Romano to Mantua in the hope of continuing the collaboration, but was

rejected; we do not know the reasons for this refusal to continue the collaboration. Penni reproduced many compositions by Raphael.

There are works today attributed to Giovan Francesco Penni, which mostly reproduce compositions by Raphael, it is plausible to think that at the death of the latter, Penni used the privileged position inside the workshop, to make many copies of these subjects from the original drawings, this because from these drawings one can notice the presence of small variations and pentimenti with signs of creative difficulty. We must therefore consider Giovan Francesco Penni as an assistant trained to act as an artistic amanuensis, capable of interpreting the ideas of the master and elaborating them in models ordered on a style strictly based on his own.

Fig.57 *Study for the Battle of Ponte Milvio Associated with Raphael Red chalk and pen on paper 22cm x 24cm*

The red pencil on paper work has recently been attributed and identified as a late drawing by Raphael, initially associated with the school. This

drawing was used for the decoration of the papal apartments in the Vatican. The compositional and stylistic details confirm that it is a preparatory study by Raphael for the famous fresco.

Fig.58 Comparison with drawing above

Comparison with the style of Sebastiano del Piombo and help from Michelangelo

The drawing in the studio seems to present elements of analogy with Michelangelo as far as the stylistic aspect is concerned. The elongated aspect of the body leads us towards a more manneristic effect distant from Raphael. Even if, as we have seen, as for the setting and type of subject, there are some points of approach to the Battle of Ponte Milvio of the Raphaellesque school.

Fig. 59

Study for Christ in the Flagellation in San Pietro in Montorio - Rome - Sebastiano del Piombo

Sebastiano del Piombo's depth in drawing is particularly evident, although in some cases helped by Michelangelo. Sebastiano remains an artist with a lesser style than Raphael. In this drawing on the side we find an excellent shading and many points of contact with the drawing technique under study. Sebastiano del Piombo was a great artist with great refinement. S. del Piombo's drawing was strongly influenced by Michelangelo over time, especially in the anatomical rendering and sense of volume. He often used charcoal and white chalk to modulate the light and thus obtain dramatic chiaroscuro. In the studio drawing, a very sculptural approach can be seen, with clear contours and exaggerated musculature to accentuate the strength of the figure. The bond between Michelangelo and Sebastiano was particularly close and strategic, in fact, Michelangelo saw in Sebastiano an ally against Raphael, and provided him with Cartoons and Drawings for some of his works. In fact,

Michelangelo did not want to compete directly with Raphael and delegated the task of opposing him to Sebastiano. Although Sebastiano was encouraged by Michelangelo against Raphael, his rivalry was indirect and in some ways there was admiration on the part of Sebastiano, who was also influenced by his compositional grace.

At the time the Battle of the Milvian Bridge was being created, Sebastiano was there in Rome and was familiar with the project; Michelangelo himself may have discussed great battles as subjects for paintings with him. By the time the Battle of the Milvian Bridge was being created, Raphael had died, so the Pope reluctantly commissioned Raphael's students to complete the work. After Raphael's death in 1520, there was a delicate moment of strong artistic and political tension regarding papal commissions, in particular the Hall of Constantine in the Vatican Palaces. At his death, Raphael had left sketches and studies of the room; Giulio Romano, who at the time was the head of the workshop and the most gifted student, and who in fact represented the heir of the technical and creative management of the works, took on the pending commissions, but the Hall of Constantine was not such an obvious commission because Pope Leo X and later Hadrian VI did not completely trust Raphael's young disciples. Constantine's victory over paganism was too important a theme for the church to be left to a student, however talented. Giulio Romano nevertheless obtained the commission, but he did not work alone, he was supported by other students such as Giovan Francesco Penni. The works were carried out on condition of continuous supervision by the papacy.

It can be assumed that Michelangelo may have been consulted and that Sebastiano del Piombo was considered as an alternative. The Battle of the Milvian Bridge, frescoed in the Hall of Constantine, shows a language still linked to Raphael, but with greater theatricality and dynamism, drawn precisely from the Julian imprint.

Sebastiano del Piombo actively tried to insert himself into the decoration of the Hall of Constantine after Raphael's death with the

support and encouragement of Michelangelo himself. Michelangelo in fact maintained that Sebastiano could have completed the work with greater quality and spirit, following an ideology more similar to his own. It can therefore be assumed that Michelangelo may have created some sketches and drawings that would then be used by Sebastiano del Piombo as a presentation for the works in the Hall. In the end, the Vatican clients did not accept because they risked having an excessive difference in style between the techniques used and Michelangelo's pupil.

There is a drawing kept at the Albertina in Vienna with the same subject, which could be the autograph work of Michelangelo, drawn for Sebastiano as a sketch to present of one of the characters of the battle and, the drawing under study, would be the copy of Sebastiano del Piombo. The drawing of the Albertina, after a series of attributions, was associated by Doctor Veronika Birke and Janine Kentesz in 1997 to Battista Franco called Semolei.

Fig.60
Attributed to Giovanni Battista Franco gen. Semolei
(Venice c. 1510 - 1561 Venice)
bloody
27.8 x 14.2 cm -Inventory number 236

A letter from Sebastiano to Michelangelo, dated September 5, 1520, confirms this attempt. In it, Sebastiano expresses his frustration at not having been chosen and mentions that Michelangelo had written to the Pope to recommend him. Thus, the commission was entrusted to Raphael's students, such as Giulio Romano and Giovanni Francesco Penni, to ensure stylistic continuity with Raphael's original designs. This episode highlights the artistic tensions of the time and the rivalry between the schools of Raphael and Michelangelo. Despite Michelangelo's support, Sebastiano failed to obtain the desired commission, but the episode testifies to his ambition and desire to assert himself in the Roman artistic panorama.

Fig. 61

*Detail for a study for the Chigi Chapel of Santa Maria del Popolo Rome
Sebastian of the Lead
Royal Collection
Black chalk drawing
For this drawing Sebastiano requested and probably received the graphic help of Michelangelo, in a letter dated 25 March 1532 there is a written testimony regarding this.*

On Good Friday 1520, Raphael died. This was announced to Michelangelo by Sebastiano del Piombo in a letter dated 12 April 1520. On the occasion of this tragedy, all of Rome was in mourning, the Pope wept for him and the people flocked to pray over his body, behind which had been placed the panel of the Transfiguration, which had not yet been completed.

Because of Raphael's death, Michelangelo's position was advantageous. On the day of Raphael's death, Michelangelo was out of Rome.

Even in the letters following Raphael's death, the tone of hatred against the workshop of Raphael's students did not diminish.

Sebastiano, immediately tried to take advantage of Raphael's death to obtain an important commission. In fact, as previously mentioned in the same letter written by Sebastiano to Michelangelo where Raphael's death was announced, he begged him to write to the Most Reverend Monsignor to grant him the Hall of Constantine, complaining that the Pope had already granted it to Raphael's apprentices, who greatly desired it and wanted to paint it in oil.

Michelangelo wrote to Cardinal Dovizi of Bibbiena, on July 3 he was received by the Cardinal who however was unable to comply with his wishes.

In the letter of September 7, 1520 Michelangelo writes that he spoke with the Pope about the terms for the work, and wrote thus:

« and all that I have spoken to the Pope, and the terms that I have used about this hope, have been out of pure love and reverence I bring to you. And through you to take vengeance, both yours and mine, and to make evil people understand that there are other demigods than Raphael of Urbino with his servants... You also write to me that you do not promise to give me affirmatives. I beg you, for the love you have for me, to bring me to a resolution on this matter; yes, or not, so that I may return the answer to the Pope, because he is sending him to see what you have written to me and I say that I have not yet received an answer: and if you want me to show your frozen letter there: give me notice of this: that I do not want to do anything against your will » .

He ends with this long speech: "I did what I wanted to do in order to work miracles and make people understand that even men who are not demigods know how to paint." Sebastiano, with all his efforts, did not succeed in his intent and under the pontificate of Clement VII the Hall of Constantine was completed by Raphael's

students. During the negotiations Luciani was offered the opportunity to paint the hall below that of Constantine; but he refused, as he expresses himself in his letters, not wanting Raphael's apprentices to paint the gilded halls, and the cellars to be reserved for him.

Sebastiano did not have the fortune of entering the good graces of Leo X, Sanzio and Michelangelo absorbed him and there was no room left for others. However, he had acquired strong relations with Cardinal Giulio de' Medici and Cardinal Rangoni, for whom he made some notable works.

All these vicissitudes occurred in the midst of major changes in the Vatican. In fact, in 1521 Pope Leo X died and was succeeded by Pope Adrian VI. This caused a great change in the field of arts and masters. The new Pope had given up the pomp and grandeur of his predecessor, and had no love for artistic subjects. He was also annoyed by the classic because he had a horror of nudes and he stopped the work on the Hall of Constantine. Even though this Pope had a good eye for Sebastiano del Piombo, so much so that he commissioned his portrait, he was unable to obtain the commission for the Hall of Constantine.

Fig.62 comparison between the work in the study on the left and the work in the Albertina

Comparison between the studio work and the drawing at the Albertina Museum in Vienna

The drawing placed in the studio was compared with a photographic image taken by Alinari relating to the drawing placed in the Albertina Museum in Vienna.

The dark color that we find in the photographic image is due to the type of shot. The technique of the work is charcoal.

The image from the Alinari Photographic Archive has the following characteristics:

Work associated with Raffaello Sanzio - Dated 1500-1512. Location Vienna Graphische Sammlung Albertina. Photo taken 2002

Size 26cm x 14cm

Below we will report a series of comparisons between the two works. On the left side the work in the studio and on the right the work located in the Albertina Museum.

The green arrow shows the two hatchings in comparison: in the work on the left we have the loss of the stroke at that point, furthermore the lines present appear to have a less dense and less linear hatching than the work in the museum.

The blue arrow indicates the lack of a line of the drawing that we find in the museum work. The presence of a number of minor details and a smaller number of lines in the work under study leads us to give a hypothesis of a copy of the artifact under study.

In the parts highlighted with red circles we find a whole series of stains caused by aging and carbon. These stains are present in the entire drawing at all levels. All these stains appear to be completely absent from the drawing placed in the study.

Fig. 63 Comparison with other details

From this second comparison, we see that the red arrow indicating the graphic trait of the lateral flourish, brings notable differences partly due to the type of pigment used which is different. On the left side we find in fact a trait with a much thicker grain size. The exact same thing can be found in the black arrow which also indicates here a less incisive trait with loss of linearity relative to the work.

Even in this comparison in the photo above, we find elements of diversification. In the green arrow on the left we find the lack of this line, while on the right we find this line. The blue lines also show variations in the line. Even in the red arrows we find the lack of correspondence. From the comparison, overall, we can say that the drawing under study seems to have been created starting from this drawing as a copy, it also emerges that the intensity of the line and a profuse hesitation in the drawing, is linked by the

Fig.64.
Comparison

copyist to make the two works as similar as possible, in fact, only by careful control can these anomalies be highlighted. Furthermore, the work cannot be a copy by the same author, as surely

the same author would have made many more variations or regrets compared to the original work, but above all, the variations he would have made would have been natural.

Comparison of the Albertina work and evaluation with the Semolei technique

Fig.65 -Albertina Collection – Vienna

27.8cm x14.2cm

Inventory number 236

Written at the bottom right “Rap. Urb.”

Historical attributions of the work:

Raphael Sanzio (Traditional).

Michelangelo's artist (Wickhoff)

No association with Raphael's circle (Fischel).

Successor of Michelangelo Buonarroti (Stix).

Circle of Michelangelo (Boy).

Semolei (Birke Veronika / Janine Kertesz).

The following work is present in the Albertina collection in Vienna and over time has undergone a series of attributions. The work in the studio is certainly created starting from this subject. The realization of the version appears to be created with a smaller size than the drawing located in the Albertina Collection.

The connecting elements appear to be very strong which determines with absolute certainty that the creator of the work in the studio had direct access to the original work in order to create his own.

Below we will examine the work kept at the Albertina with the style of the last artist to whom it was attributed, namely Semolei.

Battista Franco, known as Semolei, was a painter and engraver (Venice 1498-1561). In Rome, this artist was deeply inspired by the works of Raphael, Michelangelo and Giulio Romano, and later by his own inventions, following the tradition of Marcantonio Raimondi. He enrolled at the Accademia di San Luca in 1535. But after seeing the Last Judgement in the Sistine Chapel, he wanted to do nothing but draw for a while. He was noticed by Raffaello da Monte Lupo and was recommended by Antonio da Sangallo the Younger, who employed him in the preparations in honor of the entry of Charles V of Habsburg, both in Rome and in Florence.

The young artist stood out above all for the great skill of his drawings, which prevailed over the pictorial technique. This artist had the obsession of copying not only from Michelangelo but also from other artists because he did not have his own personal style, his inventions were lacking and lacking freshness and originality. In Florence Salomei met Vasari and became friends with Bartolomeo Ammanati with whom he went to live together with Genga of Urbino with whom he had a fruitful artistic partnership. He was in the service of Cosimo I de Medici and painted many works that were appreciated. In Rome, he entered the service of Cardinal Francesco Corner and competed with Francesco Salviati with a Saint John imprisoned by Herod, which was not up to the comparison, this because of his extreme

attention to the drawn details that took away spontaneity and color from the work as a whole.

Semolei had the ability to create complex compositions, often depicting mythological and religious scenes with numerous figures. The Albertina drawing presents a muscular tension created with energy and a dynamic musculature with the use of sfumato and cross-hatching, which models the forms and creates depth, these elements are not found in the works of Semolei.

Fig.66
Detail of the work Allegory with a bearded man sitting with a book
Metropolitan Museum
Baptist Franco
19cm x 20.5cm
Pen, brown ink, brush and watercolor

Below is a comparison between the work above by Semolei, with the drawing of the warrior kept at the Albertina Collection in Vienna. A whole series of stylistic and line parameters were evaluated. The drawing of the bearded man presents a line by Semolei that is very controlled, clean and uniform in its structure. The intensity of the line is constant and very descriptive. The anatomical study is detailed but lacks movement, it appears static with a classic body setting. The hatching is linear and homogeneous throughout the drawing. The strength of the graphic line offers a meditative sense and little theatricality of the subject. The drawing present at the Albertina Museum, has a fluid, energetic and sometimes tumultuous graphic line, the intensity of the line is very varied, at times contrasting and clear and

in other areas the line is lighter giving a rendering of high dynamism with amplified musculature. The hatching is mixed with curved, semicircular and dramatic lines. The composition with the body in torsion creates a centrifugal movement and great emotionality. The drawing thus presents itself with a very high strength and vibrant gestures. This drawing presents elements of very high expressive force, dynamic composition and vigorous graphic line, with marked emphasis on anatomical torsion and muscular tension, in contrast to the drawing of the bearded man by Semolei which has a more stable and measured style, with an excellent anatomical mastery, but with a less theatrical composition and a more sober line. This analysis suggests that the two artists have very different approaches, even if they share a certain technical refinement. However, the first drawing shows characteristics strongly associated with Michelangelo and not with Semolei.

Comparative graph that offers a cross-section of the stylistic compatibility of the different elements analyzed between the Albertina drawing associated with Michelangelo, and that of the Metropolitan Museum associated with Semolei. The sum of the different elements gives a graphic compatibility of the two artists of 47%

Fig.67 Comparison Chart

Anatomical Study and its Importance

The study of anatomy was important for an artist, whether a sculptor or a painter. The in-depth study of the relationship between the human figure and the world in which it moves was necessary for artists and theorists of the Renaissance, especially in order to organize and control space through the system of perspective.

Fig.67
Male nude with the indicated proportions
Sanguinary - Michelangelo
28.9cm x 18cm
Royal Library

The body was therefore studied in terms of measurements and proportions. For this reason, it was very often framed, enclosed and divided into diagrams and geometric schemes with figures and numbers. This element was particularly evident in Leonardo da Vinci. Among the codes of the time that most explicitly explained these elements were the codes of Leonardo, Piero della Francesca and Durer. This geometric aspect inserted into the human figure was important for building schemes in relation to architectural practice.

Some drawings by Piero della Francesca showed that he used linear and geometric grids to study the proportions of the face and skull. It was one of his students, the mathematician Luca Pacioli, who in 1509 published a treatise entitled *De Divina Proportione*. According to Pacioli, the perfect and ideal proportion is that of the golden

section, and for him, numbers have a mystical meaning.

Fig. 68 Albrecht Durer
Symmetry of Human Bodies

The study of proportion also passed through a very important figure: Leon Battista Alberti. He used the rules established by Vitruvius examining the relationships between proportions and perspective. Leonardo da Vinci also tried to establish a relationship between proportion and movements of the human figure and the perspective system. Durer also based his studies on that of Vitruvius, emphasizing the symmetry and schematization of the body. With Michelangelo, towards the end of the Renaissance, we witness a certain departure from the ideal canon, which manifested itself in the deliberate distortion and elongation of the human figure. This subjective tendency in contrast with mathematical objectivity, developed further with Mannerism and the Baroque, when the effects of musculature, facial expression and movement, interested artists more than the rules of harmony.

Fig.69
Adam (construction drawing)
Albrecht Dürer - 1504
Brown pen, proportion on the support leg and
construction lines with brown pen, pentimenti present
on the upper arms
26.2cm x 16.64cm

Fig.70
Eva (construction drawing)
Albrecht Dürer
1506 - 26.2cm x 16.5cm
Technique: Brown pen, construction lines with pen

Anatomical studies in the Renaissance represented a real sector. Regarding Michelangelo's approach, it is legitimate to assume that he too, similarly to other artists, such

as Leonardo da Vinci, used cadavers or parts of cadavers for study purposes.

Fig.71
From Michelangelo
Anatomical study of right leg with muscle marking
Technique: Sanguine
28.3cm x 20.7cm
Royal Library

This material can be defined as teaching material and was repeatedly used as a reference compendium and served preparatory purposes.

Of this type of anatomical studies, there are none directly attributable to Michelangelo, and those known today are probably those of his students and followers copied from the originals.

Given the numerous surviving copies, this suggests that there was a real anatomy course created by Michelangelo, where the muscles were labelled with letters to facilitate recognition and identification.

Unlike Leonardo da Vinci, Michelangelo was not interested in the appearance of veins, arteries and capillaries, but only in the structural articulation of the organism, especially with regard to the position of muscles and the volumetric combinations that determine the reliefs and depressions of the skin. Therefore, Michelangelo's anatomical drawings should be treated more as an artist's anatomical studies than as a medical treatise.

Fig.71 Comparison between the work studied on the left and the anatomical study of the musculature taken from a drawing by Michelangelo's students.

From this comparison it is possible to identify very interesting elements, in fact in the leg under study, we have a musculature that shows both muscular elements seen from behind and muscular elements seen from a lateral-posterior area. This aspect is very interesting because in this drawing, not only is the effect of movement guaranteed by the double lines of the leg and the variations in intensity of the stroke, but the presence of a hybrid musculature as if it were in two positions at the same time is unique. This aspect helps to make the effect of dynamism greater.

Final Considerations and Conclusions

The following study was a journey to find not only the possible creator of this drawing, but also to understand its purpose and final destination. We therefore tried to place the work within a specific context. The following are important elements of conclusion. The drawing presents stylistic and technical characteristics that are decidedly important and undoubtedly recall the Michelangelo environment, also taking up

elements of Sebastiano del Piombo's graphic practice. It can therefore be assumed that the drawing may have been created under the influence of Michelangelo. The use of the sanguine technique, with soft strokes and the chiaroscuro present through shading obtained by modular pressure, is a technique very close to that of Michelangelo, especially in preparatory drawings for frescoes. The differences that we find between this drawing compared to that of the same subject in the Abertina Museum, are given by degrees of graphic uncertainty present. As regards the musculature, it is volumetric and plastic, carefully rendered as a sculptor would have done; so since Sebastiano del Piombo was not a sculptor, this element is a distinctive sign of the direct influence of Michelangelo, who set the drawing as if it were a sculpture on paper. The figure study is perfect in its dynamic pose and twisted in the Michelangelo manner. The anatomical study is pushed and accentuated, with the hypertrophic musculature typical of Buonarroti, with the presence of a great sense of movement. Another element of relevance is the rear view of the shoulder, which focuses on the emphasis of physical power. Sebastiano del Piombo was not a draftsman of this type before meeting Michelangelo, in fact, his first Venetian drawings were much less plastic. After meeting Michelangelo and his help especially during the work of the Flagellation and the Pietà of Viterbo of 1512-1516, Sebastiano developed a more sculptural language influenced by Michelangelo. We can therefore affirm that the work in the study is the work of an artist from Michelangelo's

circle, probably created as a copy by Michelangelo, under his direct influence and with the aid of an autographed drawing by Michelangelo. As regards the anatomical study, we have on the part of the artist a good knowledge of the anatomical aspect, especially from the back of the thigh and calf. Note a clear definition of the gluteus maximus that fades towards the biceps femoris present in the external part of the thigh, which appears to be correctly oriented and well connected to the knee. The gastrocnemius muscle of the calf is clearly visible and is correctly divided into the two muscle heads, with a slight torsion that denotes the movement of the legs. Therefore, the drawing also offers the effect of posterior flexion. As regards the final insertion of the hamstring, it appears a bit too rigid, lacking softness. Another anomaly is derived from the long lateral fibula not clearly represented, which is why this drawing could have been made starting from the better structured one in the Albertina Museum. We can therefore say that from an anatomical point of view we have an anatomically plausible drawing, and the small expressive adjustments aim at emphasizing dynamism rather than real accuracy. From a stylistic point of view the helmet is clearly visible on the head, with a crest or cimiera, the decoration is that used by Renaissance artistic contexts to evoke the classical world, rather than authentic historical models. The garment on the pelvic area is a sort of "pteyges", that is, a garment made of overlapping strips of leather and cloth, typical of Roman armor, this element is strongly associated with the depictions of Roman warriors in Renaissance figurative arts. The pose is heroic, with a strong rotational movement of the torso and swing of the arm, as if he were about to throw something or to defend himself, a gesture therefore very common in the representations of ancient fighters. We could define this warrior as a representation of an ideal Roman warrior inspired by the classical world but filtered by a Mannerist aesthetic. The drawing is very refined and shows an excellent mastery of the chiaroscuro full of energy. The artistic gesture of this drawing demonstrates a conscious knowledge of anatomy, but voluntarily chooses to force some proportions to obtain greater

dramatic tension. The use of sanguine, the soft curves and the floating contour lines for the drapery and with a volumetric construction, are consistent with Michelangelo's studies with the ideal of a Roman heroic figure. In the drawing under study, the representation of the muscles, especially of the legs, shows a notable attention to volume and muscular tension, characteristic elements that we can also find in some works by Sebastiano del Piombo, such as in the Pietà of Viterbo (1512-1516), here the figure of Christ presents, in fact, a carefully modelled field, highlighting the muscular structure and the tension of the tendons, elements that recall the influence of Michelangelo. However, it is important to remember that Sebastiano del Piombo, despite collaborating with Michelangelo, did not achieve the same anatomical precision of the drawings. Although Sebastiano did not leave works with military subjects, his ability to represent heroic figures and his attention to the details of clothing are evident in works such as the Martyrdom of Saint Agatha of 1520, where the executioners wear detailed and realistic clothes. The use of the sanguine technique present in the drawing under study, presents soft strokes and shades obtained through variations in pressure, a technique that Sebastiano del Piombo used intentionally. For example, in the preparation of the Pietà of Ubeda, Sebastiano uses drawings provided by Michelangelo, which show a refined use of chiaroscuro and an accurate modeling of the body. This drawing, based on the one in the Albertina Museum, could be the work created on the inspiration of Michelangelo, who, although never directly involved in the decoration of the Vatican rooms, lent Sebastiano del Piombo drawings and support in an attempt to hinder Raphael's hegemony, and to ensure that the commission was entrusted to him. **We therefore think that the subject was conceived by Michelangelo (Albertina drawing) for Sebastiano del Piombo who in turn created his own (work in the studio).** In fact, painters of the time had to convince the client with preparatory drawings. Sebastiano, with this drawing and thanks to his relationship with Michelangelo, wanted to propose a heroic muscular style perfectly in line with the subject of the Battle of

Ponte Milvio, an event symbolic of the victory of Christianity over paganism. In conclusion, for this attribution hypothesis, we summarise the elements of strong interest below. For the technique, the use of sanguine with an energetic stroke and hints of spiral movement, consistent with the studies influenced by Michelangelo, compatible with Sebastiano del Piombo in his mature phase. The figure represented is a warrior with a helmet, marked musculature and dynamic posture which are elements absolutely consistent with a subject for the Battle of Ponte Milvio. The careful, expressive and plastic anatomy associated with a potential style of Sebastiano del Piombo compatible with a work prepared with the help of Michelangelo who provided him with the drawn models. The clothing worn by the warrior, with the plumed skirt (pteryges), the helmet with crest and the partial nudity, all elements of depictions of idealized Roman soldiers in the Renaissance and late Renaissance. It is therefore plausible to affirm that this drawing is part of a cycle of studies carried out by Sebastiano del Piombo as a proposal for the Hall of Constantine, a presentation sketch therefore intended for the Vatican evaluation commission. This drawing was made with the anatomical advice of Michelangelo , **and perhaps with his direct intervention in many points** , and represents a rare example of a military study of the graphic production of **Sebastiano del Piombo** carried out starting from a work by Michelangelo.

Conclusions

The present study conducted a multidisciplinary investigation on "Studio di Guerriero", combining technical analyses of the paper support with a stylistic, iconographic and archival examination. Scientific investigations revealed that the support is made of paper produced from hemp, linen and cotton rags, with a homogeneous thickness of 70 µm and the use of additives such as calcium and talc. The presence of regular lines (2 mm between the lines, 28 mm between the threads) and a trace of watermark, although not fully legible, contribute to the dating and identification of the origins of the support.

Observations regarding the execution technique confirm the use of sanguine, sometimes diluted, and a differentiated trimming process, with precise cuts on the upper and right margins and tears or less regular interventions on the left and lower margins. This technical evidence, together with the indication of a previous restoration intervention, provides a detailed picture of the materiality and conservation history of the work.

From an attributive point of view, the iconographic and stylistic analysis suggests a complex relationship with the Roman artistic context of the 16th century, with significant references to the works of Sebastiano del Piombo and to the attributive debate that includes figures such as Michelangelo. The absence of direct archival data requires a cautious approach to the definitive attribution.

In summary, the study has provided material data and stylistic observations that are fundamental for a deeper understanding of the "Study of a Warrior". Although the attribution question requires further comparative investigations and perhaps the use of advanced non-invasive techniques for pigment analysis, the data collected represent a significant contribution to the knowledge of the work and the context in which it was produced.

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